

Studies in 4-Aminothiazolines(VIII)

AMRIK SINGH* AND K. S. NARANG

Chemistry Department, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar

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2-Imino-3-aryl-4-amino-5-carbethoxy-4-thiazolines(III) when condensed with 2-chlorothiazoles (IV) in phenolic solutions gave 2-(2'-imino-3'-aryl-5'-carbethoxy-4'-thiazolinyl) amino-4-aryl-thiazoles (V). Derivatives of (III) when heated with ammonium thiocyanate, gave 2-imino-3-aryl-4-thioureido-5-carbethoxy-4-thiazolines (IX).

INTRODUCTION of carbethoxy and carboxamido groups in position 5-of-4-aminothiazolines have not only made these thiazolines more stable, but also useful synthetic intermediates in developing new heterocyclic systems¹⁻⁵. Here we report some unsuccessful attempts at the synthesis of bisthiazolo (3, 2-*a*; 4', 5'-*d*) pyrimidine (I) and thiazolo (4, 5-*d*) pyrimidine derivatives (II).

Anthranilic acids and esters when condensed with 2-chlorothiazoles in phenol, furnish 10: 11-thiopegans⁶⁻⁸. The parallel condensation of 2-Imino-3-aryl-4-amino-5-carbethoxy-4-thiazolines (III) with 2-chlorothiazoles (IV) did not give the expected derivatives of (I), but uncyclized intermediates 2-(2'-imino-3'-aryl-5'-carbethoxy-4'-thiazolinyl) amino-4-aryl-thiazoles (V) in very poor yields (5-percent). However, when 2-chloro-5-nitrothiazoles were used the yields of (V) improved to 50 percent as the 5-nitro group enhances the reactivity of 2-chlorine atom in (IV). The nitro derivatives of (V) were deep red coloured, high melting crystalline solids. The structure of (V) is supported by both i.r. and n.m.r. spectra.

succeed. This is probably due to withdrawal of electrons from nitrogen (*) as shown in (V) by nitro group which decreases the nucleophilic character of (*) nitrogen atom.

Ethyl-anthranilate hydrochloride when treated with potassium thiocyanate furnishes thiocyanato salt (VI) which undergoes rapid cyclization to (VII)⁹⁻¹⁰. The parallel reaction of hydrobromides of (III) and KCNS did not yield the thiocyanate(VIII) but instead gave the free base (III). However thioureas (IX), were obtained in 50 percent yields when derivatives of (III) were treated with NH₂CNS at 120°. Attempted cyclization of (IX) to (II) by keeping in ethanolic sodium hydroxide or by refluxing in ethanol alone for 10 hr did not succeed (Scheme 2).

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillaries and are uncorrected. IR. spectrum was run on a Perkin Elmer-337 grating spectrometer. N.M.R. spectrum was run on a Varian-A-60 instrument.

Scheme 1

Attempts at the cyclization of (V) ($R_1 = \text{NO}_2$) to (I) by heating in polyphosphoric acid did not

Reaction of 2-imino-3-aryl-5-carbethoxy-4-amino 4-thiazoline (III) with 2-chlorothiazole (IV) (General

* Senior author.

Scheme 2

procedure). (a) A mixture of (III) (.0038 mole) and 2-chloro-4-aryl-thiazole (IV) ($R_2 = \text{aryl}$, $R_1 = \text{H}$) (.0038 mole) was taken in phenol and heated in an oil bath at $130^\circ\text{--}140^\circ$ for 6 hr. It was cooled and treated with dilute sodium carbonate solution to remove phenol. The residue (V) separated, was filtered, washed with water, and recrystallized from ethanol.

(b) Similarly 2-chloro-5-nitrothiazoles (IV) ($R_1 = \text{NO}_2$, $R_2 = \text{aryl}$) were condensed with derivatives of (III) in phenol at 110° for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was treated with ethanol, filtered and recrystallized from dioxan : ethanol mixture (50:50).

Various derivatives of (V) synthesized are listed in table 1.

to *Bisthiazolo* (3.2-a, 4', 5'-d) *pyrimidine derivatives* (I): A solution of appropriate derivative of (V) ($R_1 = \text{NO}_2$) (1g) in freshly prepared polyphosphoric acid (3g) was heated at $150^\circ\text{--}160^\circ$ for 30 min in an oil bath. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water (30 ml) and the solid separated was found to be the starting compound (V) ($R_1 = \text{NO}_2$) as indicated by identical R_f value and undepressed mixed melting point with authentic sample on admixture.

Reaction of derivatives of (III) and ammonium thiocyanate. 2-Imino-3-aryl-5-carbomethoxy-4-aminothiazoline (.075 mole) and powdered ammonium

TABLE I. 2-(2'-IMINO-3'-ARYL-5'-CARBETHOXY-4'-THIAZOLINYL) AMINO-4-SUBSTITUTED THIAZOLES (V)

Ar	R_2	R_1	M.P. $^\circ\text{C}$	M.F.	Analysis	
					Found	Required
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	H	261	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	N, 12.52	12.28
<i>p</i> -tolyl	<i>p</i> -bromophenyl	H	215	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br}$	C, 55.26, H, 3.73	55.38, 3.83
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -bromophenyl	H	160	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Br}$	N, 11.01	3.87
<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	phenyl	H	248	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$	N, 11.60	11.15
<i>p</i> -tolyl	<i>p</i> -bromophenyl	NO_2	305	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}$	N, 12.51	12.28
<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	<i>p</i> -tolyl	NO_2	295	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	N, 12.72	12.50
					N, 13.42	13.59
					C, 52.52	52.73
					H, 3.62	3.49
<i>o</i> -tolyl	<i>p</i> -bromophenyl	NO_2	270	$\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Br}$	N, 12.80	12.50
<i>p</i> -phenetyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	NO_2	313	$\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_5\text{Cl}$	N, 13.05	12.84
phenyl	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	NO_2	290	$\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}$	N, 14.30	13.99

All these compounds were crystallized from ethanol : dioxan mixture (50:50)

IR spectra of (V) ($R_2 = p$ -bromophenyl, $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$, Ar = *p*-tolyl) run in KBr pellet, possessed absorptions at 3250, 3350 (NH str.), 1660 cm^{-1} (C = O str.).

NMR spectra of (V) ($R_2 = p$ -bromophenyl, $R_1 = \text{NO}_2$, Ar = *p*-tolyl), run in CDCl_3 possessed signals at δ 1.37 (t, 3H, $J = 7$ cps) ($\text{O-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ 2.38 (q, 2H, $J = 7$ cps), ($\text{O-CH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ 2.38 (s) (3H, CH_3); δ 7.95 (m, 1NH and 8 aromatic) and a singlet at δ 5.75 (1-2 protons, NH).

Attempted cyclization of 2-(2'-imino-3'-aryl-5'-carbomethoxy-4'-thiazolinyl) amino-4-aryl-5-nitrothiazoles (V)

thiocyanate (1.1 equivalent) were thoroughly mixed and heated in an oil bath at 120° for 10 min. The reaction mixture was cooled, treated with ethanol, the solid separated was washed with water and then with ethanol when 2-imino-3-aryl-4-thioureido-5-carbomethoxy-4-thiazoline (IX) so obtained was crystallized from dioxan. IR spectra (IX) (Ar = *o*-tolyl run in KBr absorbed at 3200 and 3400 cm^{-1} (NH stretching), 1665 cm^{-1} (C = O str.).

Various derivatives of (X) synthesized are summarized in Table 2.

TABLE 2. 2-IMINO-3-ARYL-4-THIOUREIDO-5-CARBETHOXY-4-THIAZOLINES (IX)

Ar	M.P. °C	M.F.	Analysis	
			Found percent	Required percent
<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	248	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂ Cl	N, 15.85	15.78
Phenyl	258	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	N, 17.59	17.39
<i>o</i> -chlorophenyl	235	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	N, 15.83 C, 43.73 H, 3.82	15.73 43.82 3.65
<i>o</i> -tolyl	210	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O ₂	N, 16.43	16.66
<i>p</i> -phenetyl	213	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ N ₄ S ₂ O ₃	N, 15.55	15.30

All these compounds were crystallized from dioxan.

Attempted cyclization of derivatives of (IX) to thiazolo (4, 5-*d*) pyrimidine derivatives (II). (a) Appropriate 2-imino-3-aryl-4-thioureido-5-carbethoxy-4-thiazoline derivative (IX) (1g) was dissolved in ethanol and 2 percent ethanolic NaOH (5 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr when original thiourea was recovered unchanged tlc. mmp.

(b) Alternatively suitable thiourea (IX) (1g) was refluxed in ethanol (10 ml) for 10 hr. On cooling the thiourea was recovered back without any change.

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